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Diagnostic accuracy of the rapid arterial occlusion evaluation and the Cincinnati prehospital stroke scale for the prediction of large vessel occlusion stroke: a systematic review

Precisión diagnóstica de la evaluación rápida de la oclusión arterial y la escala de accidente cerebrovascular prehospitalario de Cincinnati para la predicción del accidente cerebrovascular por oclusión de grandes vaso: una revisión sistemática

Alicia Morocho MSc.¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7860-8011>

Cristóbal Espinoza MSc.¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8608-8338>

Raisa Espinoza Inv.¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-5006-5093>

Rosangela Caicedo PhD² <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0737-9132>

Moises Cajías Dr.² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3306-2991>

Helen León MSc.² <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9119-0837>

Florencia Chancay MSc.² <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2357-7286> Catholic ¹University of Cuenca, Group for Research, Health, Science and Innovation "ISCI", Cuenca, Ecuador.

²Bolivarian University of Ecuador, Guayas, Ecuador.

*Autor de correspondencia: Alicia Morocho, Catholic University of Cuenca, Group for Research, Health, Science and Innovation "ISCI", Cuenca, Ecuador. E-mail: alicia.morocho@ucacue.edu.ec

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Abstract

Introduction: Stroke, particularly due to large vessel occlusion (LVO), is a significant cause of disability and mortality worldwide. Early identification in prehospital settings is crucial for implementing interventions such as mechanical thrombectomy. In this context, the Cincinnati Prehospital Stroke Scale (CPSS) and the Rapid Arterial Occlusion Evaluation (RACE) are useful as clinical tools to enhance the detection stroke. Evaluating their diagnostic accuracy may optimize their application in emergency services. **Materials and Methods:** A systematic review was conducted following PRISMA 2020 guidelines with the aim of evaluating the diagnostic accuracy of the RACE and CPSS scales in identifying ischemic stroke in prehospital and hospital settings. Systematic searches were conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, covering the period from January 1, 2020, to April 30, 2025. The search was supplemented by a manual review of the reference lists of included articles to identify potentially relevant additional studies. A total of 17 studies were included, for the evaluation of sensitivity, specificity, likelihood ratios (LR+ and LR-), methodological quality (assessed using QUADAS-2), and applicability of the CPSS, RACE, and their variants

(CPSS-2, d-CPSS, and RACE-4). **Results:** The CPSS scale was evaluated in 13 studies, with sensitivity ranging between 57-95% and specificity between 54.3-94%. Its LR+ ranged from 1.96 to 9.83, being higher in hospital settings or in patients with high clinical suspicion. The RACE scale was evaluated in 9 studies, with sensitivity between 56-100% and specificity between 60-91%, with LR+ values up to 8.33. Scales like RACE and CPSS showed good LR- values (some close to 0.1), making them useful for ruling out stroke in emergency settings. However, CPSS-2 showed an LR- of 0.63, which reduces its utility as an exclusion test. **Conclusion:** Both CPSS and RACE are useful tools for early detection of LVO-related stroke, especially in prehospital environments. RACE tends to offer greater diagnostic accuracy due to its more detailed assessment of neurological deficits, while CPSS stands out for its simplicity and rapid applicability. An implementation tailored to the local healthcare system is recommended, along with more prospective studies with external validation to strengthen the available evidence.

Keywords: Stroke, large vessel occlusion, evaluation scales, prehospital diagnosis, sensitivity, specificity.

Introducción: El accidente cerebrovascular (ACV), especialmente por oclusión de grandes vasos (OGV), es una causa significativa de discapacidad y mortalidad a nivel mundial. La identificación temprana en el ámbito prehospitalario es crucial para aplicar intervenciones como la tromboectomía mecánica. En este contexto, las escalas CPSS (Cincinnati Prehospital Stroke Scale) y RACE (Rapid Arterial occlusion Evaluation) se utilizan como herramientas clínicas para mejorar la detección de casos sospechosos de OGV. Evaluar su precisión diagnóstica permite optimizar su aplicación en servicios de emergencia. **Metodología:** Se incluyeron 17 estudios seleccionados por su evaluación de la sensibilidad, especificidad, razones de verosimilitud (LR+ y LR-), calidad metodológica (evaluada mediante QUADAS-2) y aplicabilidad de las escalas CPSS, RACE, y sus variantes (CPSS-2, d-CPSS y RACE-4). Los estudios fueron heterogéneos en diseño, tamaño muestral y contexto clínico (hospitalario y prehospitalario), incluyendo tanto investigaciones retrospectivas como prospectivas. **Resultados:** La escala CPSS fue evaluada en 13 estudios, con una sensibilidad entre 57% y 95% y especificidad de 54,3% a 94%. Su LR+ varió de 1,96 a 9,83, siendo más altos en entornos hospitalarios o con pacientes con alta sospecha clínica. Por su parte, la escala RACE se evaluó en 9 estudios, con sensibilidad de 56% a 100% y especificidad de 60% a 91%, con LR+ de hasta 8,33. Escalas como RACE y CPSS mostraron buenos valores de LR- (algunos cercanos a 0,1), útiles para descartar ACV en escenarios de urgencia. Sin embargo, se observó que CPSS-2 mostró un LR- de 0,63, lo que reduce su utilidad como prueba de exclusión. **Conclusión:** Tanto la escala CPSS como la RACE son herramientas útiles para la detección temprana del ACV por OGV, especialmente en entornos prehospitalarios. La RACE tiende a ofrecer mayor precisión diagnóstica gracias a una evaluación más detallada de los déficits neurológicos, mientras que la CPSS destaca por su sencillez y rapidez. Se recomienda una implementación adaptada al sistema de salud local y más investigaciones prospectivas con validación externa para consolidar la evidencia disponible.

Palabras clave: Accidente Cerebrovascular. Escalas de Valoración. Diagnóstico Prehospitalario. Sensibilidad y Especificidad. Evaluación de Resultados en Atención de Salud

At present, stroke is the second leading cause of both disability and mortality globally. The worldwide incidence of strokes has been estimated at around 13.7 million new cases per year; with roughly 87% of these being ischemic strokes, and approximately 10-20% corresponding to large vessel occlusion (LVO)¹. This condition also represents a heavy burden for public health systems, especially in low-income and middle-income countries². Early diagnosis is a cornerstone of optimal clinical management of stroke, minimizing disability and improving overall outcomes³.

Several tools have been designed and implemented seeking this swift diagnosis, allowing for improved and prioritized care objectives, and appropriate referral. Among these, the Rapid Arterial occlusion Evaluation (RACE) and the Cincinnati Prehospital Stroke Scale (CPSS) stand out for their widespread use and ease of application in out-of-hospital settings. Their clinical utility lies in the ability to rapidly identify severe cases requiring immediate specialized attention^{4,5}.

Various studies have evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of these tools. A sensitivity of 65.6% and specificity of 72.3% has been reported for the RACE scale in suburban and rural emergency services, demonstrating reasonable performance in detecting LVO in that specific setting⁶. Similarly, a sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 88% has been noted when comparing the application of the RACE scale between emergency medical technicians and neurologists, suggesting high diagnostic concordance⁷. However, variability among studies is notable: one large patient cohort reported a sensitivity of 62% and specificity of 93%⁸, while another study observed poorer performance for RACE in patients with mild symptoms (sensitivity of 28%, specificity of 97%)⁹.

The CPSS scale has also been the subject of multiple evaluations. This scale demonstrated a sensitivity of 69% and specificity of 77%, indicating greater sensitivity than RACE in mild cases¹⁰. Similarly, sensitivity and specificity values of 59% and 89%, respectively, have been reported¹¹. These discrepancies suggest that the diagnostic performance of both scales may depend significantly on the clinical context, symptom severity, and training level of prehospital personnel. In light of these heterogeneous findings, we performed a systematic review assessing the accuracy of these tools for the diagnosis of stroke across various care settings.

A systematic review was conducted following PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 guidelines, with the aim of evaluating the diagnostic accuracy of the RACE and CPSS scales in identifying ischemic stroke in prehospital and hospital settings.

Systematic searches were conducted in three electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, covering the period from January 1, 2020, to April 30, 2025. The search was supplemented by a manual review of the reference lists of included articles to identify potentially relevant additional studies.

The following Boolean operators and MeSH terms (or equivalents) were used, adapting the strategy for each database according to its specific syntax: (“stroke” OR “ischemic stroke” OR “cerebrovascular accident”) AND (“prehospital” OR “emergency medical services” OR “EMS” OR “emergency department”) AND (“RACE scale” OR “CPSS” OR “Cincinnati Prehospital Stroke Scale” OR “CPSS-2” OR “d-CPSS”) AND (“diagnostic accuracy” OR “sensitivity” OR “specificity” OR “likelihood ratio”) AND (“2020”[Date - Publication] : “2025”[Date - Publication]).

The study selection was performed by two independent reviewers in three phases: identification, screening, and eligibility assessment. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or consultation with a third reviewer.

The inclusion criteria were studies published between 2020 and 2025, in English or Spanish, that evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of the RACE, CPSS, CPSS-2, or d-CPSS scales for identifying ischemic stroke in adult populations (>18 years), and reported data on sensitivity, specificity, or likelihood ratios. In contrast, we excluded studies involving pediatric populations, editorials, narrative reviews, letters to the editor, duplicate studies, or those that did not report quantitative results on diagnostic accuracy.

From each study, the following data were extracted: author and year of publication, country of origin, study design, diagnostic tool evaluated, sample size, inclusion criteria and sample characteristics, values for sensitivity, specificity, likelihood ratios (LR+ and LR–), and assessment of methodological quality as indicated by the QUADAS-2 tool.

In this regard, the quality of the included studies was independently assessed by two reviewers using QUADAS-2, considering four domains: patient selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus.

In this systematic review, a total of 356 studies were identified through the Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed databases. After the removal of 112 duplicate records, 244 studies were screened by title and abstract. Of these, 198 were excluded for not meeting the previously defined inclusion criteria. Subsequently, 46 full-text articles were assessed, of which 29 were excluded due to methodological issues or for not providing relevant data for the objectives of the review. Ultimately, 17 studies met the established eligibility criteria and provided evidence on the diagnostic accuracy of the CPSS and RACE scales in the detection of stroke (**Figure 1**).

The analysis of these 17 included studies shows considerable variability in methodological design, sample size, and clinical context (**Table 1**). The CPSS had the largest amount of published evidence, with 13 studies, while the RACE scale was analyzed in 9 studies. The sensitivity of CPSS ranged between 57-95%, and its specificity between 54.3-94%, with positive likelihood ratios (LR+) ranging between 1.96-9.83. In the case of RACE, sensitivity ranged between 56-100%, and specificity between 60-91%, with LR+ values up to 8.33. The studies with the highest sensitivity and LR+ were those conducted in controlled hospital settings or with patients under high clinical suspicion. This variability may be attributed to differences in inclusion criteria, diagnostic methods (such as the use of MRI vs. CT), and care settings (prehospital vs. hospital).

Regarding the quality assessment using the QUADAS-2 tool, most studies presented a low risk of bias, although

some showed limitations in applicability, mainly due to retrospective design, small sample sizes, or lack of external validation. The main reported limitations included heterogeneity in diagnostic criteria, lack of comparison with other validated scales, and non-generalizable settings, such as specialized emergency services or unrepresentative populations. Despite these limitations, the results support the use of CPSS and RACE as useful ini-

tial tools for the prehospital detection of stroke, although their accuracy may vary significantly depending on the context and the population assessed.

Table 1. Summary of study characteristics, sensitivity, specificity, and likelihood ratios, along with risk-of-bias (QUADAS-2) evaluations and limitations of the studies included in the systematic review.

Authors and year	Country of origin and design	Interventions evaluated	Sample and criteria	Sensitivity/ Specificity	Groups and key characteristics	Likelihood Ratios (LR)	QUADAS-2 evaluation	Limitations
Duvekot et al., 2020 (12)	Netherlands – Prospective, multicentric study.	RACE and CPSS	1314 patients with clinical suspicion of ischemic stroke (1039 cases, 275 controls).	RACE: 65,6% / 72,3%	Prehospital emergency setting.	RACE LR+ ≈ 2,37 / LR- ≈ 0,48	Low risk of bias in all domains.	Only RACE was assessed; no homogeneous imaging criteria were applied.
Maddali et al., 2020 (13)	India – Prospective observational study.	CPSS	60 patients with clinical suspicion of stroke (42 cases, 18 controls).	79% / 95%	Hospital emergency setting.	LR+ ≈ 15,8 / LR- ≈ 0,22	High quality, small sample.	Limited sample size, unrepresentative sample.
Saberian et al., 2020 (14)	Iran – Multicentric diagnostic accuracy study.	CPSS	805 patients in an emergency setting with clinical suspicion of stroke (562 cases, 243 controls).	95% / 54,3%	Adults aged >18 years, MRI diagnosis.	LR+ ≈ 2,08 / LR- ≈ 0,09	High methodological quality.	Low specificity, no stratification by severity.
Wang et al., 2020 (15)	China – Retrospective validation study.	CPSS-2 and RACE-4	1630 patients (836 cases, 794 controls) evaluated with 8 h of symptom onset.	CPSS-2: 55% / 72%; RACE-4: 64% / 60%	Confirmed diagnosis of stroke.	CPSS-2 LR+ ≈ 1,96 / LR- ≈ 0,63	Low risk of bias for sample selection; high for applicability.	Limited applicability due to retrospective nature; incomplete data.
Disckson et al., 2021 (16)	USA – Retrospective observational study.	RACE	505 patients (440 cases, 65 controls) with clinical suspicion of ischemic stroke.	66% / 72%	Prehospital evaluation.	LR+ ≈ 2,36 / LR- ≈ 0,47	Low risk of bias for sample selection; uncertain for other domains.	Possible verification bias, no external validation.
Karimi et al., 2021 (17)	Iran – Comparative diagnostic study.	CPSS	883 patients (618 cases, 265 controls) with stroke confirmed by MRI.	78,5% / 66%	Evaluation with CPSS and PreHAST, diagnosis confirmed by MRI.	LR+ ≈ 2,31 / LR- ≈ 0,33	Moderate quality, good applicability.	No comparisons with other scales of greater complexity.
Chiu et al., 2021 (18)	Taiwan – External validation study.	CPSS	7194 patients (1231 cases, 5963 controls).	76,8% / 71,8%	Prehospital evaluation.	LR+ ≈ 2,73 / LR- ≈ 0,32	Good general quality.	Missing diagnostic confirmation by imaging.
Uchida et al., 2021 (19)	Japan – Retrospective and prospective multicentric cohort.	CPSS	1884 patients (337 cases, 1547 controls)	68% / 88%	Hospital emergency setting.	LR+ ≈ 5,67 / LR- ≈ 0,36	Good methodological quality.	No other scales were evaluated for comparison in the sample.
Gude et al., 2021 (20)	USA – Observational retrospective study.	CPSS	120 patients (87 cases, 33 controls).	92% / 79%	Hospital emergency setting.	LR+ ≈ 4,38 / LR- ≈ 0,10	Acceptable quality, small sample size.	Small sample size, no randomization.
Crowe et al., 2022 (21)	USA – Retrospective analysis.	CPSS-2 and RACE-4	13,596 patients (4228 cases / 9368 controls), data from emergency medical services linked with hospital diagnoses.	CPSS-2: 69% / 78%; RACE-4: 63% / 73%	Prehospital assessment documented by emergency medical services.	CPSS-2 LR+ ≈ 3,14 / LR- ≈ 0,40	High quality, low bias.	Retrospective design; possible errors in data from emergency medical services.
Hackett et al., 2022 (22)	United Kingdom – Comparative prospective study.	RACE	48 patients (31 cases, 17 controls) referred to center specialized in stroke management.	100% / 88%	High clinical suspicion of large vessel occlusion.	LR+ ≈ 8,33 / LR- ≈ 0	Moderate risk of bias due to sample size.	Small sample size, sample selection bias.
Tarkanyi et al., 2022 (23)	Hungary – Prospective cross-sectional study.	CPSS and d-CPSS	421 patients (183 cases, 238 controls) with first acute ischemic stroke.	CPSS: 64,5% / 87%; d-CPSS: 69,9% / 75,2%	Hospitalization due to first ischemic stroke.	CPSS LR+ ≈ 4,96 / LR- ≈ 0,41	Good quality, low bias.	Evaluation only in hospital setting, no prehospital assessments.
Nehme et al., 2022 (24)	Australia – Retrospective observational study.	CPSS	440 patients (223 cases, 217 controls).	59% / 94%	Prehospital evaluation.	LR+ ≈ 9,83 / LR- ≈ 0,44	High quality in all domains.	No validation with other scales.
Nguyen et al., 2023 (25)	Australia – External validation study with comparison of scales.	RACE	2007 patients (842 cases, 1165 controls) in emergency settings.	56% / 90%	Initial in-hospital assessment.	LR+ ≈ 5,60 / LR- ≈ 0,49	High methodological quality.	Evaluation only in hospital setting, no prehospital assessments.
Wagstaff et al., 2023 (26)	United Kingdom – Retrospective observational study.	CPSS	17,442 patients (3781 cases, 13,661 controls).	76% / 68%	Prehospital evaluation.	LR+ ≈ 2,38 / LR- ≈ 0,35	Good general quality.	No stratification of results by severity.
Ganesh et al., 2024 (27)	Canada – Prospective multicentric study.	RACE and CPSS	1000 patients (800 cases, 200 cases), symptom onset ≤6 h and blood glucose >2.5 mmol/L	RACE: 66% (21–91%) / CPSS: 57% (32–69%) / Specificity: CPSS: 85% (37–94%)	Assessment by degree of neurological deficit.	RACE LR+ ≈ 4,71 / CPSS LR+ ≈ 3,8	High applicability, high heterogeneity.	High heterogeneity in results and inclusion criteria.
Krebs et al., 2025 (28)	Germany – Prospective observational study.	RACE and CPSS	741 patients (323 cases, 418 controls) with suspicion of ischemic stroke.	RACE and CPSS: 59% / RACE: 91%, CPSS: 89%	Prehospital differential diagnosis.	RACE LR+ ≈ 6,56 / CPSS LR+ ≈ 5,36	Low risk in all domains.	No external validation; no data about timeline of care.

CPSS: Cincinnati Prehospital Stroke Scale; LR+: Positive likelihood ratio; LR-: Negative likelihood ratio; QUADAS-2: Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies-2.

This systematic review analyzed the diagnostic accuracy of the CPSS and RACE scales—as well as other derived tools, such as the CPSS-2, d-CPSS, and RACE-4—for the detection of stroke, particularly in prehospital and emergency contexts. Overall, both CPSS and RACE demonstrated acceptable levels of sensitivity, though with considerable variability in specificity, reflecting the impact of the differences in methodological design, sample size, and clinical application settings.

Some findings were particularly remarkable when assessing positive likelihood ratios (LR+). Maddali et al. (13) in India reported an LR+ of 15.8 for the CPSS, suggesting excellent capacity to confirm the presence of stroke in a hospital setting, despite its limited sample size ($n = 60$) and lack of population representativeness. Similarly, Nehme et al. (24) in Australia ascertained an LR+ of 9.83 for CPSS for prehospital evaluation, supporting its usefulness in real-world emergency scenarios. In contrast, other studies such as that by Wang et al. (15) showed LR+ values below 2, which limits its utility in diagnostic screening.

Regarding the RACE scale, LR+ values ranged from 2.36 (16) to 8.33 (22), indicating greater heterogeneity in performance. This variability may be explained by the clinical setting (prehospital vs. specialized), the degree of clinical suspicion, or the severity of neurological deficits in the sample. Indeed, Hackett et al. (22) studied patients referred to a high-specialization center with a strong suspicion of LVO, which may have enhanced diagnostic performance.

Negative likelihood ratios (LR-) also provided valuable information. Saberian et al. (14) and Gude et al. (20), reported LR- values close to 0.1, suggesting a good capacity for ruling out stroke. This is critical in contexts where rapid decision-making is required to avoid unnecessary treatment or delays in care. However, other investigations, such as Wang et al. (15), reported an LR- of 0.63 for CPSS-2, limiting its utility as an exclusion test.

Notoriously, sample sizes and demographic characteristics varied widely. Studies such as that by Wagstaff et al. (26), with over 17,000 patients, and Chiu et al. (18), with over 7,000 cases, allow for generalization of findings, although they may be influenced by data entry errors and retrospective biases. In contrast, more controlled studies, like those by Ganesh et al. (27) and Krebs et al. (28), used multicenter prospective designs with stricter clinical criteria, such as time of symptom onset and blood glucose levels, which improves internal validity at the expense of generalizability.

In terms of methodological quality, assessed using the QUADAS-2 tool, most included studies showed low risk of bias in at least one domain, although common limitations were common, such as selection bias, lack of external validation, or use of retrospective data. Crowe et al. (21) and Nguyen et al. (25) presented high overall quality, although their analyses were based on emergency medical service records and hospital databases, which may introduce classification errors.

Closer analysis of the available data allows for further characterization of the utility of the RACE and CPSS. The RACE scale assesses stroke severity through scoring of specific neurological deficits. A rapid review comparing RACE with other prehospital scales for detecting LVO found that RACE is a valid and feasible clinical tool in out-of-hospital settings, with diagnostic accuracy comparable to other scales, though slightly lower than that of the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS), which is used in hospitals (29). A more recent study evaluated the predictive value of the RACE scale for LVO in ischemic stroke patients, concluding that it is a simple and valuable tool for predicting LVO within the first 24 hours of symptom onset (30). Moreover, its implementation in regions such as Catalonia has demonstrated improvements in early detection of LVO strokes and effective referral to stroke units (31).

On the other hand, the CPSS is a simple tool used by emergency personnel to detect signs of stroke. A systematic review and meta-analysis found that with a threshold of ≥ 2 , CPSS is useful for identifying LVO stroke; which may be critical for guiding patients to specialized care, both in prehospital and hospital settings (32). However, the quality of evidence was rated as very low, indicating the need for additional studies to confirm these findings. Other investigations have found that although CPSS is widely used, it may have lower sensitivity compared to more complex scales, such as the Field Assessment Stroke Triage for Emergency Destination (FAST-ED), or the Los Angeles Motor Scale (LAMS) (33, 34).

Thus, both RACE and CPSS appear to offer advantages in the rapid identification of LVO in patients with ischemic stroke. RACE provides a more detailed assessment of neurological deficits, while CPSS is simpler and quicker to apply. The choice between them may depend on available resources and the training of personnel in different clinical settings (29, 32, 34).

Indeed, the RACE and CPSS scales are valuable tools for the prehospital detection of LVO in patients with ischemic stroke. While both have demonstrated usefulness, current evidence suggests that RACE may offer greater diagnostic precision in certain contexts. Further research is required to strengthen the evidence base and guide the optimal implementation of these scales in clinical practice (30, 32, 34).

The CPSS and RACE scales are useful tools for the prehospital identification of stroke, particularly in settings where rapid clinical decision-making is required. Both scales demonstrate acceptable levels of sensitivity and specificity, although with considerable variability attributable to methodological design, population characteristics, and clinical context. The RACE scale appears to exhibit more robust diagnostic performance in specialized settings, whereas CPSS stands out for its simplicity and broad applicability. However, methodological limitations and the variable quality of evidence highlight the need for prospective, multicenter studies that assess their performance in more diverse populations and real-world environments. These tools should be considered as part of a comprehensive early stroke care strategy, complemented by optimized personnel training and adequate diagnostic resources.

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